

Size-Effect induced by cold-forming on the Strength of a HSS Truss Joint

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ABSTRACT

A scale-down of joints for experimental tests is typically based on nominal material properties without considering the effects of cold forming. In this study, the effects of enhanced strength on the scaling of joints are studied numerically with the welded K-type joints made of mild steel and of high strength steel (HSS). The joint consisted of two cold-formed tubular braces, a plate chord, and one division plate. The effects of the enhanced strength from cold forming on the scaling joint were studied for the joint in different scales. The strength enhancement was based on material tests on the tension coupon extracted from the tubular bracings in two scales. The results showed that the cold-forming enhanced the yield strength and the ultimate strength at corners of smaller profiles about 14%-16% and 10%-16% more than at same locations of larger bracings. In the joint model without considering the enhanced strength of corners, the maximum load of the joint scaled by the scaling factor is about 95% to 98% of the maximum load of the full-scale joint using the material properties measured from the profiles studied. In the model considering the enhanced strength of corners, the use of the scaling factor led to the joint maximum capacity that was up to 9% lower than the maximum load received from the models with full scale dimensions. The maximum load of the joint is mainly affected by the difference in the ultimate strengths between the profiles in two scales. The observations are valid for both mild steel and HSS joints. The studies indicate that the strength of the joint scaled up by scaling factors needs to be reduced up to 10% considering the size-effects of cold forming. For the similar joints with different dimensions, further studies are necessary if the strength reduction are proposed for design use.

Keywords: high strength steel, scaling, welded tubular joints, slim-floor truss system

1 INTRODUCTION

In building construction, structural use of high strength steel (HSS) leads to a higher strength-to-weight ratio and reduces carbon footprint because less material is used, and less weight is transported. Slim floor systems with load-bearing steel trusses enable column-free building spaces and their flexible use, accelerate construction, and facilitate the integration of building services. The slim-floor system was invented in Nordic countries and has been used worldwide (1). One application of using cold-formed HSS tubular sections as truss members in a novel truss-slim-floor system is shown in *Fig. 1* (2). The truss has a WQ-beam as its upper chord, square hollow sections as its braces, and a steel plate as its lower chord. The hollow-core slab can be installed on the lower edges of the WQ-beam. The joint in the corner of the truss is a K-type joint, which is reinforced by the division plate welded to the two hollow-section braces and the lower chord.

Fig. 1 Slim floor system with studied truss joint.

Although the EN 1993-1-12 (3) extends the applicability of design rules for joints in the EN1993-1-8 (4) up to S700, these two design standards have no rules specified for designing the joint studied in this research. The studies in (5)-(8) have covered different types of joint but not this type of K-joint. Therefore, a series of numerical studies have been carried out in investigating the structural behaviour of this specific joint. (9)-(11) To validate the numerical models and to determine the limit load by strain criteria, the experimental tests have also been performed on mild steel and HSS joints (12)(13). For the experimental tests, the specimens were scaled down using the dimensional analyses because of the available testing facilities. In the determination of scaling factors, it was assumed that the full-scale and the scaled tubular sections had the same effective yield strength. However, the results of tensile coupon tests showed that the effective yield strengths of full-scale and scaled tubular sections differed because of the size-effects of cold forming (14). Therefore, the objective of this research is to study the effect of strength enhancement from cold-forming on the scaling factors and on the limit load of the joint in tension-controlled failure using numerical analysis.

The outline of the paper is as follows. The finite element (FE) models were first created and validated by test results. Using the validated FE models, the scaling factors were then verified. In the end, the limit loads determined for the joints in different scales are compared using the material models proposed for the tubular sections of mild steel and HSS.

2 FE MODELS BASED ON THE TESTED JOINTS

2.1 Tested joint scaled from a full-scale truss joint

Fig. 2 shows the models used for the joint inside a steel truss and the joint studied experimentally. Using the truss model and loading conditions, the dimensions of full-scale truss-joint were determined in (10). For representing the behaviour of the joint inside the truss, the effects of the boundary conditions and loading conditions were studied in (11), and the final dimensions of the full-scale isolated joint were obtained as shown in Fig. 2 (b).

For testing the joint in the laboratory conditions, the studies in (11) showed that the load-carrying capacity of the full-scale joint is 12 times larger than that of the loading cell. Using the equations presented in Annex A, the factor for scaling the length is 3.46, i.e., the dimension of the scaled down joint is 3.46 times smaller than those of its full-scale peer. The length of the chord was observed to affect the joint failure. If the chord is five times longer than its width, the joint failed in the local buckling of the compressed brace whereas the chord four times longer than its width led to the fracture of the tensioned brace. For easy installation of the joint specimen to the test setup, three endplates were welded to the two braces and the chord. The chord was intentionally lengthened to ensure the failure of compressed brace and functionally a pinned boundary condition for the chord as described by the deformation mode shown in Fig. 2 (c) because of the clamped conditions of the endplate. The

test specimen of the S355/S420 joint is shown in *Fig. 2* (d). To ensure that the failure occurred close to the joint, the test specimen of the S700 joint was stiffened by welding the plates to the end of the two bracings. The dimensions of the joint models in different scales are presented in Table 1.

Fig. 2 From the joint inside the truss to the tested joint a) full-scale truss joint b) full-scale isolated joint c) scaled down joint d) tested joint.

Table 1 Dimensions of joint models in full-scale and in a scale of 3.46.

Scale	Chord			Division plate			Braces			
	L_0 [mm]	b_0 [mm]	t_0 [mm]	L_p [mm]	h_p [mm]	t_p [mm]	L_i [mm]	b_i [mm]	t_i [mm]	α [deg]
Full scale	1750	350	40	340	200	25	600	150	10	45
Test scale	505.2	101	11.54	98.1	57.7	7.21	173.2	43.3	2.89	45

2.2 FE models based on the tested joints

Numerical simulations were performed using the Abaqus/Standard FE Analysis software version 2018 (15) considering both geometrical and material non-linearity. To catch the local buckling of the compression braces observed in the tests, the built-in solver based on the arch-length method was used. The FE models were created for the joint in the testing conditions (*Fig. 3* (a)). The joint was modelled by 3D solid elements with quadratic formulation. The mesh details are shown in *Fig. 3* (b).

The boundary conditions of FE models were defined by reference points within or near the ends of the braces and chord as shown in *Fig. 3* (c). To simulate the experiments as accurately as possible, the distance between reference points were adjusted to consider the locations of the real hinges in the test setup. Two components of forced displacements were applied to the reference point of the tension bracing: one is along the centreline of the tension brace (along U3 local) because of the movement of the loading actuator and the other is an in-plane lateral component (along U2 local) caused by the small lateral movement of the load actuator. To improve the computational efficiency, the model comprised one of the symmetrical halves of the joint. In the FE analyses, the material models were based on the material properties of S420 and S700 steels measured from the tubes and plates for the fabrication of the joint specimens (16). The coupons were taken from the centre of each face of the tubular sections.

Fig. 3 FE models based on tested joint a) Tested joint b) mesh details c) boundary and loading conditions.

3 VALIDATION OF FE MODELS AND VERIFICATION OF SCALING FACTORS

For transferring the load, *Fig. 4* showed that the load and displacement curves of FE analyses and tests can be divided into four stages: linear stage, inelastic stage, the maximum load, and unloading stage. In terms of the 4-stage load-transferring mechanism, the load and displacement curves between numerical and test results matched reasonably. Compared to the tested joint, the joint model entered inelastic stage earlier but reached the same maximum load with a similar deformation. The failure of the joint was triggered by the local buckling of the compressed brace in both FE analyses and tests. Because of the slight differences in the locations and paths of buckling, the joint unloading progressed faster in FE analysis than in the tests. Because of the different buckling mechanism in details, the tension bracing had the same calculated maximum load as in tests but a 19% larger displacement. The reasonable agreements of failure modes and load-displacement curves between numerical and experimental results validate the FE models.

Fig. 4 Validation of FE models by test results for mild steel joint a) load-deformation curves b) deformation mode from FE analyses c) deformation mode from tests.

Because of the slightly different dimensions between the tested and the scaled joint, a new FE model based on the dimensions of scaled down joint was created for verifying the scaling factors. The values of displacement and force received by this new model were multiplied by the scaling factors of 3.46 and 3.46^2 , respectively. A FE model of the full-scale joint was also created. The load-displacement curves of the scaled up and the full-scale joint are compared in *Fig. 5*. The ratio between the load magnitudes of the scaled up and full-scale joint is 0.99 for both braces. However, as the ratio between corresponding displacements was about 0.87, the agreement between loads is slightly better than that between displacements. A reasonable compatibility of load-displacement curves received by scaled up and full-scale models verifies the scaling factors.

Fig. 5 Verification of scaling factors using the load-deformation curves of the scaled down and upscaling models.

As pointed out in (11) (13), the load exerted on either the tension bracing or compression bracing can lead to either local buckling in the compressed brace or fracture in the tension brace close to the joint region. Depending on the failure mode, the limit load can be determined as the maximum load reached in a compression-controlled failure or as the load corresponding to predefined principal strain in a tension-controlled failure. In (13), principal strains of 5% and 2% were proposed for the mild steel and HSS joint, respectively.

4 EFFECTS OF COLD FORMING ON THE JOINT SCALING

4.1 Enhanced strength of tubular section due to cold forming

To study the effects of the enhanced strength due to cold forming on the limit load of the joint in a tension-controlled failure, the mechanical properties of the tubular sections were determined from tensile coupon tests (14). The specimens were prepared according to SFS-EN ISO 6892-1 [26]. For the tubular sections of $40 \times 40 \times 2.4(2.6)$ mm, the specimens were prepared non-standardly so that the measured strength represented a localized value instead of an average value. However, the results were calibrated by the results of testing the specimens prepared according to the standard.

The specimens were cut out in the rolling directions. In the cross-section of $150 \times 150 \times 10$ mm, the specimens were cut out of four locations: centres of the flat surfaces, corners, flat surfaces close to corners, and flat surfaces with weld seams. In the section of $40 \times 40 \times 2.6(2.4)$ mm, the specimens were cut out of three locations due to limited dimensions: centres of the flat surfaces, corners, and flat surfaces with weld seams. The locations of specimens extracted from these two profiles are shown in *Fig. 6* (a) and (b), respectively.

Fig. 6 The locations of tension coupons a) Dimensions b) locations in the profile of 150×150×10 mm c) locations in the profiles of 40×40×2.6 mm.

The specimens were tested on the universal tensile machine, and the measured stress-strain curves at corners and at the centre for the mild steel and HSS profiles are shown in Fig. 7 and Fig. 8, respectively. For all the studied tubular sections, the cold forming enhanced the strength about 20% to 30% and reduced the ductility about 9% to 38% more at corners than at centres, respectively. At both corners and centres, the strength enhanced of 12% to 20% more in the smaller profile than in the larger profile. The dimensions of the profile clearly affected the material properties.

To study the effect of cold forming on the limit load of joint in different scales, the double-stage equations proposed in (14) and (16) based on the measured properties are presented as

$$\varepsilon = \begin{cases} \frac{\sigma}{E} + \left(\alpha \frac{f_y}{E}\right) \left(\frac{\sigma}{f_y}\right)^n & \text{for } \sigma \leq f_y \\ \frac{\sigma - f_y}{E_y} + \left(\varepsilon_u - \varepsilon_y - \frac{f_u - f_y}{E_y}\right) \left(\frac{\sigma - f_y}{f_u - f_y}\right)^m + \varepsilon_y & \text{for } f_y < \sigma \leq f_u \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where

$$\varepsilon_y = (1 + \alpha) \left(\frac{f_y}{E}\right) \quad (2)$$

In the equations, σ is stress, ε is strain, E is elasticity modulus, α is yield offset coefficient, f_y is yield strength, E_y is tangent modulus, f_u is tensile strength, ε_u is strain at f_u , ε_y is yield strain, n is the first hardening exponent, and m is the second hardening exponent.

Fig. 7 Comparison between the stress and the strain curves received from the tests and the curves calculated by using the proposed equations for mild-steel profiles of a) 150×150×10 mm b) 40×40×2.6 mm.

Fig. 8 Comparison of between the stress and strain curves received from the tests and the curves calculated by using the equations proposed for HSS profiles of a) 150×150×10 mm b) 40×40×2.6 mm.

The parameters of E , α , n , m , E_y and f_y were fitted to the results of tensile tests. The mean values of the test-based material properties used in FE models for S420 and S700 steels are shown in Table 2 and Table 3, respectively. The stress and strain curves given by using these equations are also presented in Fig. 7 and Fig. 8.

Table 2 Mean values of test-based properties used in FE models for S420 steel

Specimens from	Qty.	Sample location	E [GPa]	f_y [MPa]	f_u [MPa]	f_u/f_y [-]	α [-]	ε_y^* [-]	E_y [GPa]	ε_u^* [-]	n [-]	m [-]
40x40x2.6	3	Centre	173.8	522.0	567.1	1.09	0.51	0.5	20.01	0.9	5.58	12.04
CoV [%]-	-	-	2.1	1.0	1.5	2.5	15.0	7.9	19.4	10.3	7.3	29.4
40x40x2.6	3	Corner	170.15	705.52	740.0	1.05	0.61	0.7	17.9	1.1	6.86	6.34
CoV [%]-	-	-	6.2	2.0	2.3	1.3	12.9	4.2	10.9	5.1	26.0	28.0
150x150x10	3	Centre	204.9	465.9	541.16	1.16	1.00	0.5	18.46	6.1	2.3	12.38
CoV [%]-	-	-	6.6	2.8	0.9	3.7	6.0	6.3	35.7	19.7	17.0	25.2
150x150x10	3	Corner	193.7	607.6	636.8	1.05	0.64	0.5	11.92	1.0	7.82	7.24
CoV [%]-	-	-	2.1	0.4	0.3	0.2	2.8	1.5	6.0	0.8	5.5	30.5

* $\times 10^{-2}$

Abbreviations: Pl. = plate; CoV = coefficient of variation; Qty. = quantity; Drctn. = direction; RD = rolling direction;

Table 3 Mean values of test-based properties used in FE models for S700 steel

Specimens from	Qty.	Sample location	E [GPa]	f_y [MPa]	f_u [MPa]	f_u/f_y [-]	α [-]	ε_y^* [-]	E_y [GPa]	ε_u^* [-]	n [-]	m [-]
40x40x2.4	3	Centre	180.64	816.9	827.08	1.07	0.43	0.6	241.46	1.0	7.07	11.12
CoV [%]	-	-	1.9	0.5	0.7	0.9	9.1	1.3	8.7	10.1	6.5	21.4
40x40x2.4	4	Corner	173.49	976.88	1027.35	1.05	0.37	0.8	22.74	1.1	7.11	7.84
CoV [%]	-	-	1.4	1.8	1.1	1.3	3.6	1.4	18.9	7.1	20.9	29.1
150x150x10	3	Centre	218.01	670.86	827.59	1.24	0.66	0.51	38.59	2.2	2.78	16.21
CoV [%]	-	-	10.4	4.9	0.3	5.3	15.3	9.2	12.9	1.6	11.9	20.9
150x150x10	3	Corner	229.86	853.94	930.81	1.09	0.49	0.6	22.09	1.5	5.62	11.70
CoV [%]	-	-	5.9	2.4	0.2	2.2	9.3	7.2	20.1	5.5	27.8	7.5

* $\times 10^{-2}$

Abbreviations: Pl. = plate; CoV = coefficient of variation; Qty. = quantity; Drctn. = direction; RD = rolling direction;

4.2 Effects of cold forming on the maximum load of the studied joints in different scales

To study the effects of the cold forming on the scaling of the joint, FE models in different scales were created. In all the joints, the load was applied to the brace in tension. The maximum load and its associated displacement for the joint models studied are shown in Table 4.

Table 4 Comparisons of the maximum load between FE results.

	Scale	Tubular sections used for		S420 joint	S700 joint
		joint model	material model	Max. load N_{max} [kN]	Max. Load N_{max} [kN]
(1)	1/3.46	40x40	40x40 (flat)	247.0	366.1
(2)	1.0	x3.46	--	2893.4	4383.1
(3)	1.0	150x150	40x40 (flat)	2856.8	4329.0
(4)	1.0	150x150	150x150 (flat)	2815.0	4180.1
(5)	1/3.46	40x40	40x40 (flat + corner)	258.9	381.8
(6)	1.0	x3.46	-	3099.8	4570.3
(7)	1.0	150x150	150x150 (flat + corner)	2836.6	4211.0
scaling			$N_{(3)}/N_{(2)}$	0.98	0.98
			$N_{(4)}/N_{(2)}$	0.97	0.95
			$N_{(7)}/N_{(6)}$	0.91	0.92
Cold forming			$N_{(7)}/N_{(4)}$	1.01	1.01
			$N_{(5)}/N_{(1)}$	1.07	1.04

In the model without considering the corner enhancement, the maximum load of the joint scaled up by 3.46 matched well with the maximum load received from the full-scale models using the material properties measured from the smaller tubular section and from the larger tubular sections. The ratio of the maximum load between by using full-scale models and by multiplying the scaling factor of 3.46^2 is varied from 0.95 to 0.98. The results indicate that the scaling factor was not affected by the differences in the values measured for the yield strength between the smaller profile and the larger profile as the yield strength of smaller tubular section was about the 12% higher than that of the larger profile. On the other hand, the maximum load of the joint is affected more by the ultimate strength. Between two profiles, the differences of the tensile strength were about 5%. These observations are valid for both mild steel and high strength steel joints.

For the joint model considering the enhanced strength at corners, the scaling factor is clearly affected by the differences in the enhanced ultimate strength produced by cold forming. The yield strength and the ultimate strength were respectively about 14%-16% and 10%-16% higher in the smaller profile than in the larger profile. The maximum loads scaled up by 3.46 is about 8%-9% higher than the maximum load of the joint modelled using the full-scale dimensions. The results were similarly validated by the ratios between scaled models with and without inclusions of the corner strength

($N_{(7)}/N_{(4)} = 1.01$) and the ratios between full-scale models ($N_{(5)}/N_{(1)} = 1.04$ to 1.07). The observations are valid for both mild steel and HSS joints.

4.3 Effects of cold forming on the limit load of the studied joints in different scales

To study the size-effects on the limit load of the joint, the FE analyses were made for the joints using nominal material properties both in a scale of 1/3.46 and in full scale. The limit loads were determined with the allowable principal strains of 2% and 5%. The limiting strain was determined using a control volume forming a triangle close to the welds on the surface of the side face of the tension brace. The limit loads received from different FE models created for mild steel and HSS joints are listed in Table 5.

Table 5 Limit load of different mild steel joint models and its comparison with code-based value

	Scales	Tubular sections used for		Mild steel joints		HSS joints	
		Joint model	Material model	$N_{2\%}$ [kN]	$N_{5\%}$ [kN]	$N_{2\%}$ [kN]	$N_{5\%}$ [kN]
(1)	1.0/3.46	40x40	40 x 40 (nominal)	190.6	207.9	306.2	327.5
(2)	1.0/3.46	40x40	40x40 (flat)	221.6	240.8	344.4	367.2
(3)	1.0/3.46	40x40	40x40 (flat + corner)	232.9	256.8	355.6	381.9
(4)	3.46/3.46	x3.46	40 x 40 (nominal)	2282.2	2489.4	3665.3	3920.9
(5)	3.46/3.46	x3.46	40x40 (flat)	2653.2	2882.5	4122.7	4395.7
(6)	3.46/3.46	x3.46	40x40 (flat + corner)	2788.3	3074.4	4257.5	4572.3
(7)	1.0	150x150	150x150 (nominal)	2297.9	2440.9	3453.4	3891.9
(8)	1.0	150x150	150x150 (flat)	2488.0	2768.9	3887.1	4248.4
(9)	1.0	150x150	150x150 (flat + corner)	2597.1	2861.6	4005.3	4288.4
scaling			$N_{(7)}/N_{(4)}$	1.01	0.98	0.94	0.99
			$N_{(8)}/N_{(5)}$	0.94	0.96	0.94	0.97
			$N_{(9)}/N_{(6)}$	0.93	0.93	0.94	0.94
Small scale			$N_{(2)}/N_{(1)}$	1.16	1.16	1.12	1.12
			$N_{(3)}/N_{(1)}$	1.22	1.24	1.16	1.17
Full scale			$N_{(8)}/N_{(7)}$	1.08	1.13	1.13	1.09
			$N_{(9)}/N_{(7)}$	1.13	1.17	1.16	1.10

Table 5 shows that the size-effects induced by cold-forming reduced the limit load approximately 6%-7%. The reduction can be observed from the ratios of the limit loads predicted by the full-scale models using material models either including or excluding the corner effects and by the full-scale model using nominal material properties. The ratio is varied from 0.93 to 0.99. As the yield strength of smaller tubular section was about 12% higher than that of the larger profile, the results indicate that the scaling factor was affected by the differences of yield strength measured between the smaller profile and the larger profile. The similar ratio can be observed for both mild steel and HSS joint.

As shown in Table 5, for mild steel joint, the limit loads predicted using the models considering corner enhancement are approximately 24% and 17% higher than that predicted using the models excluding the corner enhancement for the scaled joint and for the full-scale joint, respectively. For the HSS joint, the same ratios are around 17% and 10%, respectively. The results indicate that the enhancement induced by cold forming affects the limit load more in the joint with smaller profiles than with larger profiles. The corner enhancement affects more in mild steel joint than in HSS joint.

For both scaled and full-scale joints, Table 5 also shows that the loads with the limit strains of 2% and 5% are approximately from 90% to 93% and from 97% to 99% of the maximum load, respectively. The results indicated that, for the cold-formed steel joint, the use of a limit strain of 2% is more conservative than the use of a limit strain of 5%. The observations are applicable for both mild steel and HSS joints.

5 SUMMARY

The high strength steel (HSS) trusses integrated with slim-floor system can challenge the applicability of current design standards to dimensioning the cold-formed tubular joint, and the capacity of facilities available for experimental tests. When joints are scaled down for experimental tests, typically their scaling are based on nominal material properties without considering the effects of cold forming. The results of tensile coupon tests showed that strength enhancements in original and scaled tubular sections differed. At corners, the enhancement of the yield strength and the ultimate tensile strengths were approximately 14%-16% and 10%-16% more in smaller profiles than in larger ones. Considering the enhanced strength at corners, the calculated maximum load of the scaled-down joint is up to 9% less than the maximum load received from the models with full scale dimensions. The reduced maximum load of the full-scale joint is mainly caused by the cold-forming-induced size-effects on the ultimate strengths and the limit load of the studied profiles. The observations are valid for both mild steel and HSS joints. The studies indicate that the strength of the studied joint scaled up by scaling factors needs to be reduced up to 10% considering the size of cold-formed profiles. For the similar joints in other dimension, further studies are necessary if the strength reduction will be used in design. In addition, because of the corner enhancement, the limit load of the joint increased approximately 13%-22%. The increase is about 7% larger in the joints with smaller profiles than with larger profiles. The 7% increase was observed when the limit loads between mild steel and HSS joint were compared. If the effects of the enhancement on the increase of joint strength are considered in design, further studies are required.

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ANNEX A

For an axially loaded member, the dimensionless product, π , is defined as

$$\pi = \frac{N}{\sigma \cdot A} \quad (1)$$

in which N is the axial force, σ is the stress, and A is the cross-sectional area. When the complete similarity is maintained two models, the following relation is satisfied, i.e.,

$$\pi_s = \pi_f \rightarrow \frac{N_s}{\sigma_s \cdot A_s} = \frac{N_f}{\sigma_f \cdot A_f} \quad (2)$$

where subscripts s and f represents scaled down and full-scale model, respectively. The factor for scaling the cross-section, S_A , is represented as

$$S_A = \frac{A_s}{A_f} = \frac{N_s}{\sigma_s} \cdot \frac{\sigma_f}{N_f} \quad (3)$$

If the material strength of two models is the same, the factor for scaling the cross-sectional area becomes

$$S_A = \frac{A_s}{A_f} = \frac{N_s}{N_f} \quad (4)$$

The factor for scaling the length, S_L , is represented as

$$S_L = \sqrt{S_A} = \sqrt{\frac{N_s}{N_f}} \quad (5)$$